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When is so much enough? On the presence of women in Italian universities and their participation in funded research projects and publications

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Introduction and theoretical background

Women are less likely than men to be funded. This may be due to differences in their scientific merits (Grimpe, 2012) as well as by gender stereotypes which identify women as less competent and committed (Lawson et al., 2021; Lerchenmueller & Sorenson, 2018). There is little empirical evidence on this topic, partly because of problems with the data available to do gender analyses (Kleinberger-Pierer et al. 2020; O’Connor, 2021).

Interestingly, to the best of our knowledge, no one has analysed the matter under the lens of organisational behaviour by applying the *Queen Bee (QB) syndrome*. The term was introduced by Staines et al. (1974), and it indicates the tendency of women to underestimate the abilities and ambitions of other women, especially if junior, as a career advancement strategy adopted in male-dominated organisations to contend with gender-stereotypical expectations. Some studies have adopted this concept to explain the underrepresentation of women in academia (Bagues et al., 2017; Ellemers et al., 2004; Faniko et al., 2021) by attributing it to different stereotypical perceptions of male and female academics. First, shared knowledge that women are more likely than men to suffer from their dual responsibilities at work and at home may lead people to suspect that it is more difficult for women than for men to display the more than full-time devotion to science that is expected from scientists (Etzkowitz et al., 1992). As a result, female scientists are perceived as generally less committed to (crucial aspects of) their work than their male colleagues, which may harm their career progress. Second, the organisational culture in academia defines career success in terms of the masculine stereotype. Successful women characterise themselves in highly masculine terms and indicate extreme career ambition— even more than their male colleagues (Ellemers et al., 2004). While this may clarify their abilities and goals, it reinforces stereotypical thinking as accurately describing what to expect from other women. Successful women distancing themselves from the gender stereotype further leads them to underestimate the competence and ambition of more junior women (Ellemers et al., 2004). As a result, successful senior women generally resist measures

to secure equal opportunities and are reluctant to mentor junior colleagues (Derks, van Laar, et al., 2011).

Whereas some interpret these findings as being characteristic of women in general, a growing body of evidence confirms the notion that QB responses emerge as a strategy to cope with gender bias in organisations (Ellemers & Barreto, 2008; Faniko et al., 2016). Specifically, QB responses were found mostly among women holding senior positions, who showed low gender identification at the beginning of their career and had experienced gender discrimination as their career advanced (Derks, Ellemers, et al., 2011). Further, experimental research demonstrated that being reminded of gender bias triggered these responses among women who identified weakly with their gender group at work (Derks, van Laar, et al., 2011).

However, these responses were not found when women were reminded of situations at work where they were judged based on their merit. These findings suggest that QB responses do not occur as a matter of course but emerge when women suffer discriminatory career experiences or when they consider these experiences. Similar self-group distancing responses were observed among cultural minorities (both men and women) who advanced to higher professional levels (Derks et al., 2015).

Aim and Contribution

We aim to demonstrate that women's success in attracting research funding may be ascribable to similar mechanisms. To do so, we rely on the Italian PRIN projects, which are government-funded national research projects, financed from 2007 to 2020. Similarly to the academic context, women's participation and success in funded research projects are still rare. Considering the Italian situation, across the PRIN calls from 2007 to 2020, women who participated accounted for 28% of the total, a percentage which decreases to 22% when considering only the principal investigators. Regarding the PRIN calls of 2017 and 2020, data about both participants and winners are available, and women make up 30% of the participants and 32% of the winners.

By distinguishing eventual QB responses, we collect data on the representativeness of women in each Italian university as the percentage of female academics to the total number of academic staff consisting of full professors, associate professors, tenure and untenured researchers. We compare this information retrieved by the website of the Italian Ministry of Universities (MUR) with the gender indicators of the Leiden Rankings: number of female authorships of a university $A(F)$, number of female authorships as a proportion of a university's total number of authorships $PA(F)$, and number of female authorships as a proportion of a university's number of male and female authorships $PA(F|MF)$.

In fact, we aim to demonstrate that (i) a high share of women in the university faculty is associated with a low level of women's commitment to PRIN projects and (ii) universities characterised by a high share of publications from women are more likely to exhibit a high level of women commitment in PRIN projects.

Results and Discussion

In the Italian systems, as in most HE systems worldwide, female academics suffer a delay in entering the system, as women have massively started to participate at university in relatively recent times. Table 1 shows that women are mainly gathered in the categories of tenure researchers, RTDA and RTDB. The highest percentage (48.4%) is concentrated in the category

of tenure researchers. The percentage grows due to the ageing of the female academic staff between 2010 and 2018 which was not counterbalanced by new entrants.

Table 1. Distribution of female academics according to their academic rank in percentage.

Role	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Full professors	18.1	18.5	18.8	19.1	20.1	20.6	20.9	21.1	21.4	21.6	22.2	23	23.7	24.8
Associate professors	33.4	33.5	33.8	34.1	34.3	34.6	34.9	35	35.6	36.5	37.2	37.5	38.4	39.3
Tenure researcher	45.2	45.2	45.1	45.2	45.3	45.3	45.4	45.6	46.4	47.6	47.9	48.4	49.2	49.5
Untenured researchers (RTDA & RTDB)						42.9	43.3	43.6	43.1	42.7	41.9	42.6	42.9	43.7

Table 2 shows the average indexes distinguishing by university typology (private, doctoral and public) sorted by average number of female principal investigators over average number of projects across the PRIN calls years, in percentage ($N_{piF}/N_{pr}(\%)$), in decreasing order. The remaining indexes shown in the table are the average number of participants to PRIN calls (N_p), the average number of female participants (N_{pF}), the average number of female principal investigators (N_{piF}), the ratio between the last two quantities ($N_{pF}/N_{p}(\%)$), the average number of projects submitted to the calls (N_{pr}). The averages are computed over the different PRIN calls years data: 2007, 2008, 2009, 2011, 2012, 2015, 2017 and 2020.

Private universities systematically overperform public universities both in terms of women participation and women principal investigators (35% vs 14% and 12% vs 4%), whereas doctoral schools exhibit the highest women participation rate.

Table 2. Women's participation and productivity indexes by university typology.

Typology	N_p	N_{pF}	N_{piF}	$N_{pF}/N_p(\%)$	N_{pr}	$N_{piF}/N_{pr}(\%)$
private	62.6	15.7	3.3	35.3	56.6	12.7
doctoral	65.3	8	2.5	38.5	65.3	6.3
public	304.4	86.2	13.8	14.3	285.1	4.4

Table 3 shows the top 10 universities in terms of project leadership, i.e. the percentage of projects whose principal investigators belong to a specific university in relation to the total number of projects where the participants belong to that specific university. Small private and doctoral universities show the highest ratio. The first public university is “La Sapienza”, which is the biggest one in Italy.

Table 3. Top 10 universities according to the percentage of principal investigators over the number of projects per university.

University	Np	N_PIs	N_PIs/Np(%)	Npr	Npi/Npr(%)	Type
Roma Università Europea	2	2	100	2	100	private
Firenze Università telematica "Italian University line"	9	5	55.6	9	55.6	private
Pisa Scuola normale superiore	93	45	48.4	93	48.4	doctoral
Pavia Istituto universitario di studi superiori	13	6	46.2	13	46.2	doctoral
Trieste Scuola internazionale superiore di studi avanzati	92	35	38.0	92	38.0	doctoral
Roma Università "Campus Bio- Medico"	46	14	30.4	41	34.2	private
Roma Università telematica internazionale "UNINETTUNO"	3	1	33.3	3	33.3	private
Aosta Università degli studi	9	3	33.3	9	33.3	private
Roma Università degli studi "La Sapienza"	1131	335	29.6	1023	32.8	public
Roma Libera Università Maria SS.Assunta (LUMSA)	17	5	29.4	16	31.3	private

The situation slightly changes when we consider the top 10 universities according to the percentage of women principal investigators over the number of projects per university (see Table 4). Small and private universities thus come out to be the most virtuous according to the index $N_{piF}/N_{pr}(\%)$, which captures the university representativeness in terms of women leading projects (PI).

Table 4. Top 10 universities according to the percentage of women principal investigators over the number of projects per university.

University	Np	NpF	NpiF	Np/NpF(%)	Npr	NpiF/Npr(%)	Type
Roma Università Europea	2	1	1	100	2	50	private
Roma Università telematica "Guglielmo Marconi"	5	3	1	33.3	5	20	private
Roma Libera Università Maria SS.Assunta (LUMSA)	17	11	3	27.3	16	18.8	private
Pavia Istituto universitario di studi superiori	13	3	2	66.7	13	15.4	doctoral
Roma Università "Campus Bio-Medico"	46	12	5	41.7	41	12.2	private
Aosta Università degli studi	9	2	1	50	9	11.1	private
Vercelli Università del Piemonte Orientale " A. Avogadro"	154	59	16	27.1	145	11	public
Urbino Università degli studi "Carlo Bo"	95	28	8	28.6	94	8.5	public
Modena e Reggio Emilia Università degli studi	279	100	21	21	264	8	public
Roma Università degli studi "La Sapienza"	1131	362	80	22.1	1023	7.8	public

Figure 1 shows two scatter plots. On the y axis, there is the number of PRIN projects led by a woman (as principal investigator), on the left-hand side x-axis there is the percentage of female academic staff, and on the right-hand side x-axis, there is the proportion of female authorship respectively. Doctoral universities do not appear in the right-hand side scatter plot as they are not included in the Leiden ranking database. On the left side, the linear trend describes a slightly negative relationship between the percentage of projects with women as PIs and the percentage of women in the academic staff for private and doctoral universities, viceversa for public institutions. This may indicate that public universities with a high percentage of women create an environment that is more supportive of women. The reason can be twofold, as it can be either a matter of size or it can be that women are likely to act as mentors. An indicator that can help to address the question is represented by the linear trend on the right side of Figure 1. Women participation as PIs is positively correlated to the percentage of publications authored by women regardless of the university typology and the slope is far higher than the previous one. It may be derived that scientific merits of women make them more eligible to be PIs of research projects but also make them less worried about their supremacy position over the other women, which may increase the collaboration and support among them.

This is in line with extant studies on the topic. Specifically, Ellemers et al. (2004) distinguished between a form of commitment directed at individual advancement at work (*career-oriented* commitment) and a form of commitment that derives from a devotion to the collaboration with one's co-workers (*team-oriented* commitment). To the extent that women are generally more communion-oriented than men (Ashmore, 1981; Ellemers et al., 1998), this may also be expressed at work, in the sense that female workers might be relatively willing to display behaviour that helps their colleagues or benefits the organisation as a whole (organisational citizenship, see Schnake, 1991; Smith et al., 1983).

Figure 1: Scatter plots of the number of women-led projects VS percentage of female academic staff (left hand side) and of the number of women led projects VS proportion of female authorship (right hand side).

Conclusion

In the last decade, several actions have been undertaken by different institutions to promote women's careers in academia and increase female representation through gender equality programmes and action plans (see LERU, 2019).

The share of female students graduating from universities now exceeds that of male students, and the share of women pursuing an academic career is slowly increasing.

Despite the larger influx of female students and junior academics, relevant statistics continue to indicate a so-called *scissor* effect between the genders that persists through different cohorts of men and women. Even in disciplines where women have been overrepresented among PhDs and at early career stages for many years (Clay, 2017; European Commission, 2019).

There is reason to believe that stereotypes about women in science persist and impede their career progress (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2020). Continuing indications of sexism and gender bias in academia suggest that the QB phenomenon may still be present today. This may lead to the provocative conclusion that recent measures intended to prevent biases against women may help perpetuate them. Specifically, involving senior female scientists in supervision and review procedures may harm rather than help the cause it is intended to serve, as there are chances that this eventually results in the provision of less rather than more encouragement and opportunities to young female scientists. This, in turn, may discourage women's participation in research projects as well. Nonetheless, to better

understand the Queen Bee syndrome, it would be useful to distinguish between disciplines and academic ranks. Women's behaviour may be thus related to the scientific area where they operate and whether they climb the ladder (Bagues et al., 2017). We aim to perform these further analyses in the near future. Similarly, venues for future research may be tackling the limitations of the data (Kleinberger-Pierer et al., 2020) considering the inhomogeneous availability of data on the PRIN calls, the availability of publication gender data averaged over a 5-years time window and for a limited number of Italian universities in the Leiden Rankings.

References

- Ashmore, R. D. (1981). Sex Stereotypes and Implicit Personality Theory. In *Cognitive Processes in Stereotyping and Intergroup Behavior* (pp. 37–82). Erlbaum. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315668758-8>
- Bagues, M., Sylos-Labini, M., & Zinovyeva, N. (2017). Does the gender composition of scientific committees matter? *American Economic Review*, *107*(4), 1207–1238. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.20151211>
- Clay, R. A. (2017). Women outnumber men in psychology, but not in the field's top echelons. *Monitor on Psychology*, *48*(7), 18–21.
- Commission, E. (2019). *She figures 2018*.
- Derks, B., Ellemers, N., van Laar, C., & de Groot, K. (2011). Do sexist organizational cultures create the Queen Bee? *British Journal of Social Psychology*, *50*(3), 519–535. <https://doi.org/10.1348/014466610X525280>
- Derks, B., van Laar, C., Ellemers, N., & de Groot, K. (2011). Gender-bias primes elicit queen-bee responses among senior Policewomen. *Psychological Science*, *22*(10), 1243–1249. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956797611417258>
- Derks, B., van Laar, C., Ellemers, N., & Raghoe, G. (2015). Extending the Queen Bee Effect: How Hindustani Workers Cope with Disadvantage by Distancing the Self from the Group. *Journal of Social Issues*, *71*(3), 476–496. <https://doi.org/10.1111/josi.12124>
- Ellemers, N., & Barreto, M. (2008). Putting your own down: How members of disadvantaged groups unwittingly perpetuate or exacerbate their disadvantage. In *Diversity at Work* (pp. 202–262). <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511753725.009>
- Ellemers, N., De Gilder, D., & Van Den Heuvel, H. (1998). Career-Oriented Versus Team-Oriented Commitment and Behavior at Work. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, *83*(5), 717–730. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.83.5.717>
- Ellemers, N., Van Den Heuvel, H., De Gilder, D., Maass, A., & Bonvini, A. (2004). The underrepresentation of women in science: Differential commitment or the queen bee syndrome? *British Journal of Social Psychology*, *43*(3), 315–338. <https://doi.org/10.1348/0144666042037999>
- Etzkowitz, H., Kemelgor, C., Neuschatz, M., & Uzzi, B. (1992). Athena unbound: Barriers to women in academic science and engineering. *Science and Public Policy*, *19*(3), 157–179. <https://doi.org/10.1093/spp/19.3.157>

Faniko, K., Ellemers, N., & Derks, B. (2016). Queen Bees and Alpha Males: Are successful women more competitive than successful men? *European Journal of Social Psychology*, *46*(7), 903–913. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ejsp.2198>

Faniko, K., Ellemers, N., & Derks, B. (2021). The Queen Bee phenomenon in Academia 15 years after: Does it still exist, and if so, why? *British Journal of Social Psychology*, *60*(2), 383–399. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjso.12408>

Grimpe, C. (2012). Extramural research grants and scientists' funding strategies: Beggars cannot be choosers? *Research Policy*, *41*(8), 1448–1460. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2012.03.004>

Kleinberger-Pierer, M., Pohn-Weidinger, S., & Grasenick, K. (2020). Fair projects-bad data? Evaluating the gender balance in science projects. *fteval Journal for Research and Technology Policy Evaluation*, (50), 60-71.

Lawson, C., Geuna, A., & Finardi, U. (2021). The funding-productivity-gender nexus in science, a multistage analysis. *Research Policy*, *50*(3). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2020.104182>

Lerchenmueller, M. J., & Sorenson, O. (2018). The gender gap in early career transitions in the life sciences. *Research Policy*, *47*(6), 1007–1017. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2018.02.009>

LERU. (2019). *Equality, diversity and inclusion at universities: The power of a systemic approach*.

National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and M. (2020). *Promising practices for addressing the underrepresentation of women in science, engineering, and medicine: Opening doors*. The National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/25785>

O'Connor, P. (2021). Gender equality: a neglected or rhetorical dimension of rankings in higher education?. In *Research Handbook on University Rankings*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

Schnake, M. (1991). Organizational Citizenship: A Review, Proposed Model, and Research Agenda. *Human Relations*, *44*(7), 735–759. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001872679104400706>

Smith, C. A., Organ, D. W., & Near, J. P. (1983). Organizational citizenship behavior: Its nature and antecedents. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, *68*(4), 653–663. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.68.4.653>

Staines, G., Tavis, C., & Jayaratne, T. E. (1974). The queen bee syndrome. *Psychology Today*, *7*(8), 55–60. <https://doi.org/10.1037/e400562009-003>